

Examination of Exercise Addiction and Narcissism in University Students

Üniversite Öğrencilerinde Egzersiz Bağımlılığı ile Narsisizm Arasındaki İlişkinin İncelenmesi

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Abstract

The aim of our study is to examine exercise addiction, awareness of exercise addiction and narcissism in university students at various physical activity levels. Related variables were measured with the Exercise Addiction Scale, Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale and Narcissistic Personality Inventory. While there was no significant relationship between the evaluation parameters in university students who do not exercise regularly, there was no significant relationship between awareness of exercise addiction and narcissism in students who have been doing sports for 0-2 years, and between the leadership dimension of narcissism and awareness of exercise addiction in students who have been doing sports for 3-5 years. It was observed that there were significant relationships between the awareness dimension, and between exercise addiction and awareness of exercise addiction in university students who have been doing sports for more than 5 years. Conducting multifactorial evaluations that may lead to the emergence of exercise addiction in university students and planning awareness training for exercise addiction with the results obtained from these evaluations can help establish balance in the social lives of these students.

Keywords Exercise addiction, Awareness of exercise addiction, Narcissism, University student.

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Introduction

Nowadays, Exercise, one of the keys to a healthy life, reduces the risk of many chronic diseases and improves quality of life and cognitive function. However, in case of excessive exercise, people may be negatively affected socially, psychologically and physiologically. In the literature, this condition is called exercise addiction (Karaağaç et al., 2022). Although exercise addiction has 6 components: psychological state change, tolerance, conflict, withdrawal, relapse and salience, it can also cause social, medical and financial problems in addition to obsessive-compulsive aspects (Weinstein & Szabo, 2023). Primary exercise addiction develops in the absence of other disorders. It involves addictive and challenging exercise, and the reward is directly related to performing the activity. Secondary exercise addiction, on the other hand, occurs in another established illness, such as eating disorders or various body image dysfunctions, including anorexia nervosa and bulimia nervosa. In secondary exercise addiction, high exercise volume is effective at achieving a goal unrelated to exercise; therefore, reward is only indirectly related to exercise performance (Zou et al., 2022).

Narcissism is defined as “a pervasive need for grandiosity, admiration, and a lack of empathy that begins in early adulthood and occurs in a variety of contexts.” Characteristics such as believing that they are unique, believing that they can only be understood by high-status people, interpersonal exploitativeness, lack of empathy, jealousy and arrogant behavior are observed in people with narcissistic orientation (American Psychological Association, 1994). According to some authors, Narcissism is characterized by a fear of emptiness and lack of meaning rather than a sense of “greatness.” Characteristic signs of narcissistic people are fits of rage or tears when what they do is not perfect enough in their eyes or when something questions their pride and self-love (Stranieri et al., 2021).

In their study examining exercise addiction in university students, Çingöz and Mavibaş (2022) did not find a significant difference in the exercise addiction levels of students from different faculties/departments. However, they stated that there were significant differences in exercise addiction levels according to daily exercise duration (Çingöz & Mavibaş, 2022). Uçar (2019) investigated the relationship between exercise addiction and narcissism in his study on individuals aged 18-65 and stated that there are significant relationships between the level of narcissism and the level of exercise addiction. In addition, he also stated that there was a negative relationship between the participants' ages and their exercise addiction levels (Uçar, 2019). Although there have been studies on exercise addiction in university students and the relationship between exercise addiction and narcissism in adults (Uçar, 2019; Çingöz & Mavibaş, 2022), there was no similar study in the literature at the time of the research regarding the relationship between these two factors in university students and also the awareness of exercise addiction.

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between exercise addiction, awareness of exercise addiction and narcissism in university students who do and do not do sports.

Material and Methods

Research Group (Population-Sample)

The population of the research was determined as (Anonymized) University Faculty of Sports Sciences students. GPower 3.1 package program was used to calculate the sample size. According to 85% test power ($1-\beta$), 95% confidence ($1-\alpha$), and effect size $d=0.65$ one-tailed independent samples t test analysis, the number of samples to be taken in each group was determined as 34 (Faul et al., 2007; Demir & Cicioğlu, 2022).

Our study included 136 university students aged 18-25 who had not suffered any injury until 6 months before the data collection date. Students were divided into 4 groups: those who do not exercise regularly, those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years, those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years, and those who have been doing sports for more than 5 years. The participants were evaluated using the Exercise Addiction Scale, Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale and Narcissistic Personality Inventory-13.

Volunteers who had not suffered any physical injury in the last 6 months at the time of the study were included in the study. Volunteers with any psychiatric disorders and volunteers who had previously participated in any study on exercise addiction or narcissism were not included in the study.

Data Collection Tools

Data collection was done face to face between 12/12/2023-15/01/2023. Data were collected from (Anonymized) University Faculty of Sports Sciences students. Volunteers participating in the study were divided into 4 groups. The 1st Group consists of students who do not exercise regularly, the 2nd Group consists of university students who have been doing sports for 0-2 years, the 2nd Group consists of university students who have been doing sports for 3-5 years, and the 3rd Group consists of university students who have been doing sports for more than 5 years. After collecting the demographic information of the participants, the following evaluation methods were applied to all groups.

Data Collection/Processing Method

Exercise Addiction Scale

It was used to evaluate the participants' exercise addiction levels. Demir et al. It was developed by (Demir et al., 2018). The scale has a 3-factor structure. The first factor is called "Excessive Focus and Emotion Change" and consists of the first 7 items. The second factor, "Postponement of Individual-Social Needs and Conflict", consists of 6 items (items 8-13). The third factor consists of 4 items (items 14-17) under the name "Tolerance Development and Passion". The highest score that can be obtained from the scale is 85, and a high score indicates that there is a high level of exercise addiction. The score ranges of the Exercise Addiction Scale are evaluated as "1-17 in the normal group, 18-34 in the low-risk group, 35-51 in the risk group, 52-69 in the addicted group, and 70-85 in the highly addicted group" (Demir et al., 2018).

Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale

It was used to evaluate the participants' awareness of exercise addiction. It was developed by Demir & Cicioğlu (2022). It has 15 items and 3 sub-dimensions. Each item is evaluated as "strongly disagree (1)", "disagree (2)", "undecided (3)", "agree (4)" and "strongly agree (5)". One of the 3 sub-dimensions, Awareness of the Effect on Emotions, consists of the

first 7 items, and the Awareness of the Effect on Socialization sub-dimension is 8-11. items, and the General Awareness subscale consists of the last four items. The Awareness of its impact on emotions subscale indicates awareness of the effect of exercise addiction on the management of emotions. The Awareness of the Effect on Socialization subscale evaluates awareness regarding the degree of impact of exercise addiction on the individual's social life and communication. The General Awareness subscale indicates the level of awareness of the negative physical effects of exercise addiction on the body. The total score of Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale can be as low as 15 and as high as 75. It is stated that as the score increases, the level of awareness regarding exercise addiction increases (Demir & Cicioğlu, 2022).

Narcissistic Personality Inventory-13

Used to assess narcissism. It consists of 13 items. Gentile et al. It was developed by (Gentile et al., 2013). The Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Doğan & Çolak (2020). Each item is evaluated as "strongly disagree (1)", "disagree (2)", "undecided (3)", "agree (4)" and "strongly agree (5)". There are 3 sub-dimensions. The leadership/authority subscale consists of the first 4 items, and the grandiosity/exhibitionism subscale consists of 5-9 items. Among the items, the claiming/exploitativeness sub-dimension is 10-13. It consists of substances. Evaluation is made on a sub-dimensional scale. The highest score that can be obtained from the 1st sub-dimension is 20 points, the highest score that can be obtained from the 2nd sub-dimension is 25 points, and the highest score that can be obtained from the 3rd sub-dimension is 20 points (Doğan & Çolak, 2020).

Data Analysis

SPSS 28.0 (IBM, 2021) package program was used in the statistical analysis of the data. Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk and Skewness-Kurtosis values were used to evaluate the normality of the data. One-Way Analysis of Variance method was used to compare the evaluation parameters between groups. As a result of this analysis, data with unequal variance distribution were evaluated with the Tukey method. Pearson test was used in intra-group correlation analysis of the data. Cases where the P value was below 0.05 were considered statistically significant results.

FINDINGS

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the study groups.

Variables	X̄	SD
Age (Year)		
Those who do not play sports	21.53	2.46
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	21.40	2.45
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	21.41	2.52
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	21.44	2.59
Exercise Addiction Scale		
Those who do not play sports	53.20	12.65
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	53.73	13.15
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	54.83	12.95
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	55.22	13.12
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale (Awareness of the Impact on Emotions)		
Those who do not play sports		
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	27.43	4.97
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	27.54	5.01
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	27.44	5.12
	27.47	5.10
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale (Awareness of its Impact on Socialization)		
Those who do not play sports		
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	12.19	4.07
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	12.24	4.15
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	12.44	4.17
	12.37	4.18
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale (General Awareness)		
Those who do not play sports	9.48	4.67
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	9.50	4.70
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	9.64	4.73
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	9.41	4.63
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale (Total Score)		
Those who do not play sports	49.11	9.93
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	49.28	10.40
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	49.53	10.62
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	49.26	10.49
NPI-13 Leadership Score		
Those who do not play sports	3.42	0.86
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	3.45	0.86
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	3.49	0.85
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	3.50	0.84
NPI-13 Exhibitionism Score		
Those who do not play sports	3.02	0.85
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	3.01	0.84
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	3.01	0.83
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	3.01	0.81
NPI-13 Exploitativeness Score		
Those who do not play sports	3.24	0.87
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	3.23	0.84
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	3.22	0.84
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	3.22	0.84
NPI-13 Total Score		
Those who do not play sports	8.88	2.14
Those who have been doing sports for 0-2 years	9.70	2.02
Those who have been doing sports for 3-5 years	9.73	1.98
Those who have been doing sports for >5 years	9.74	1.94

Descriptive statistics of the study groups are presented in Table 1.

Table 2: Relationship between evaluation parameters in university students who do not exercise regularly.

		Age (Year)	Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	Awareness of its impact on socialization	General Awareness	Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale Total Score	Leadership	Exhibitionism	Exploitativeness
Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	0.163								
	p	0.121								
Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	Correlation Coefficient	-0.005	0.054							
	p	0.486	0.349							
Awareness of its Impact on Socialization	Correlation Coefficient	0.009	0.175	0.186						
	p	0.475	0.105	0.091						
General Awareness	Correlation Coefficient	0.257	0.099	-0.042	0.576					
	p	0.032	0.240	0.382	0.000					
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	0.120	0.141	0.532	0.807	0.698				
	p	0.197	0.157	0.000	0.000	0.000				
Leadership	Correlation Coefficient	0.236	0.213	-0.029	0.059	0.214	0.096			
	p	0.044	0.063	0.418	0.338	0.062	0.248			
Exhibitionism	Correlation Coefficient	-0.028	0.306	0.027	0.153	0.094	0.125	0.599		
	p	0.421	0.013	0.425	0.137	0.252	0.186	0.000		
Exploitativeness	Correlation Coefficient	0.114	0.482	-0.084	0.029	0.013	-0.038	0.396	0.548	
	p	0.209	0.000	0.275	0.419	0.464	0.394	0.002	0.000	
NPI-13 Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	0.127	0.406	-0.023	0.128	0.117	0.099	0.788	0.866	0.786
	p	0.182	0.001	0.435	0.181	0.202	0.239	0.000	0.000	0.000

There are significant relationships between Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale and NPI-13 sub-dimensions in university students who do not exercise regularly ($p < 0.05$). There are also significant relationships between the NPI-13 subscales, Exhibitionism and Exploitation, and the Exercise Addiction Scale score ($p < 0.05$). The relationship between evaluation parameters in students who do not exercise regularly is presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Relationship between evaluation parameters in university students who have been doing sports for 0-2 years.

		Age (Year)	Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	General Awareness	Awareness of its Impact on Socialization	Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale Total Score	Leadership	Exhibitionism	Exploitativeness
Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	0.016								
	p	0.476								
Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	Correlation Coefficient	-0.160	-0.154							
	p	0.276	0.284							
General Awareness	Correlation Coefficient	-0.149	-0.037	0.054						
	p	0.291	0.446	0.421						
Awareness of its impact on Socialization	Correlation Coefficient	-0.225	-0.148	-0.047	0.561					
	p	0.201	0.292	0.432	0.012					
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale Total	Correlation Coefficient	-0.229	-0.129	0.433	0.720	0.787				
	p	0.196	0.317	0.047	0.001	0.000				
Leadership	Correlation Coefficient	0.097	-0.178	0.340	0.302	-0.084	0.286			
	p	0.360	0.255	0.099	0.127	0.378	0.141			
Exhibitionism	Correlation Coefficient	0.229	-0.217	-0.089	-0.306	-0.131	-0.198	0.224		
	p	0.196	0.210	0.371	0.125	0.314	0.231	0.202		
Exploitativeness	Correlation Coefficient	0.263	-0.209	0.111	0.089	0.032	0.029	0.596	0.339	
	p	0.163	0.218	0.341	0.372	0.453	0.458	0.007	0.100	
NPI-13 Total	Correlation Coefficient	0.184	-0.229	0.238	0.193	-0.015	0.189	0.863	0.548	0.823
	p	0.247	0.196	0.187	0.237	0.477	0.242	0.000	0.014	0.000

It was observed that there were significant relationships between Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale sub-dimensions Awareness of the Effect on Socialization and General Awareness ($p=0.01$) and NPI-13 sub-dimensions Exploitation and Leadership ($p=0.007$) in students who had been doing sports for 0-2 years. The relationship between evaluation parameters in students who have been doing sports for 0-2 years is presented in Table 3.

Table 4: Relationship between evaluation parameters in university students who have been doing sports for 3-5 years.

		Age (Year)	Exercise Addiction Total Score	Awareness of its Impact on Socialization	Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	General Awareness	Exercise Addiction Awareness Total	Leadership	Exhibitionism	Exploitativeness
Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	-0.135								
	p	0.285								
Awareness of its Impact on socialization	Correlation Coefficient	-0.307	0.334							
	p	0.094	0.075							
Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	Correlation Coefficient	-0.051	0.434	0.272						
	p	0.416	0.028	0.123						
General Awareness	Correlation Coefficient	0.081	-0.181	0.471	-0.250					
	p	0.367	0.223	0.018	0.144					
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	-0.066	0.224	0.853	0.356	0.673				
	p	0.391	0.171	0.000	0.062	0.001				
Leadership	Correlation Coefficient	0.029	0.321	0.272	0.562	0.042	0.392			
	p	0.452	0.084	0.123	0.005	0.430	0.044			
Exhibitionism	Correlation Coefficient	-0.210	-0.087	0.138	0.525	-0.208	0.023	0.313		
	p	0.187	0.358	0.281	0.009	0.189	0.462	0.090		
Exploitativeness	Correlation Coefficient	0.421	0.041	0.264	0.268	0.082	0.429	0.544	0.017	
	p	0.032	0.431	0.130	0.127	0.366	0.030	0.007	0.471	
NPI-13 Total Score	Correlation Coefficient	0.078	0.214	0.302	0.608	-0.125	0.326	0.872	0.520	0.700
	p	0.372	0.183	0.098	0.002	0.300	0.080	0.000	0.009	0.000

In students who have been doing sports for 3-5 years, Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale subscale is between Awareness of its impact on emotions and Exercise Addiction Scale scores ($p=0.028$), NPI-13 subscale is between Leadership and Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale - Awareness of its impact on emotions ($p=0.005$), NPI-13 is between Exploitativeness and Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale - Awareness of its impact on emotions ($p=0.009$), it was observed that there were significant relationships between NPI-13 Total score and Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale - Awareness of its impact on emotions. The relationship between evaluation parameters in students who have been doing sports for 3-5 years is presented in Table 4.

Table 5: Relationship between evaluation parameters in university students who have been doing sports for more than 5 years.

		Age (Year)	Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	Awareness of its Impact on Socialization	General Awareness	Exercise Addiction Awareness Total Score	Leadership	Exhibitionism	Exploitativeness
Exercise Addiction Scale Total Score	Correlation	0.092								
	Coefficient p	0.243								
Awareness of the Impact on Emotions	Correlation	-0.036	0.422							
	Coefficient p	0.392	0.000							
Awareness of its Impact on Socialization	Correlation	-0.017	0.131	0.313						
	Coefficient p	0.448	0.160	0.007						
General Awareness	Correlation	-0.238	-0.105	0.070	0.471					
	Coefficient p	0.034	0.211	0.297	0.000					
Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale Total Score	Correlation	-0.126	0.250	0.600	0.835	0.667				
	Coefficient p	0.169	0.027	0.000	0.000	0.000				
Leadership	Correlation	0.099	0.198	0.269	0.061	-0.164	0.128			
	Coefficient p	0.227	0.064	0.019	0.321	0.106	0.165			
Exhibitionism	Correlation	0.010	0.247	-0.069	-0.104	-0.070	-0.114	0.244		
	Coefficient p	0.471	0.028	0.301	0.215	0.299	0.192	0.030		
Exploitativeness	Correlation	-0.028	0.226	0.045	-0.014	-0.010	0.078	0.383	0.376	
	Coefficient p	0.415	0.041	0.366	0.458	0.470	0.276	0.001	0.002	
NPI-13 Total Score	Correlation	0.051	0.279	0.132	0.002	-0.087	0.069	0.711	0.735	0.766
	Coefficient p	0.349	0.015	0.158	0.493	0.255	0.300	0.000	0.000	0.000

Among university students who have been doing sports for more than 5 years, there is a difference between Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale -General Awareness score and age ($p=0.03$), between Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale total score and Exercise Addiction Scale total score ($p=0.02$), between NPI-13 Leadership score and Exercise Addiction Awareness Scale - Awareness of its impact on emotions score ($p=0.01$) between NPI-13 Exploitativeness score and Exercise Addiction Scale Total score ($p=0.02$), between NPI-13 Exploitation and Exercise Addiction Scale total score It was observed that there were significant relationships between ($p=0.04$) and NPI-13 total score and Exercise Addiction Scale total score ($p=0.01$). The relationship between evaluation parameters in students who have been doing sports for more than 5 years is presented in Table 5.

Discussion

This When the study results are examined, there is no significant relationship between

the evaluation parameters in university students who do not exercise regularly, while there is no significant relationship between awareness of exercise addiction and narcissism in students who have been doing sports for 0-2 years, between awareness of narcissism and exercise addiction in students who have been doing sports for 3-5 years, and between awareness of exercise addiction and narcissism in students who have been doing sports for more than 5 years. It has been observed that there are significant relationships between exercise addiction and awareness of exercise addiction in university students who do sports.

Reasons such as individuals' character traits, expectations from life, and the contribution of exercise to social life and physical and mental health may push people to implement intensive exercise programs (Dinardi et al., 2021). The physical harm of exercise addiction is mostly seen as long-term risks such as musculoskeletal injuries. Psychological damages are observed with sudden changes in the person's mood when exercise is not possible (Landolfi, 2013).

In a study conducted with a university student, it was reported that the student spent more than his budget on sports due to his exercise addiction, started to experience more widespread psychological disorders as a result of these expenses, and started to physically harm himself as a result of these disorders (Griffiths, 1997). In addition, another university student was reported to have hip fracture as a result of exercising for hours during the day (Polivv & Clendenen, 1993).

Exercise addiction contains classic components that are also found in other addictions. For this reason, a multidisciplinary approach is of great importance in its treatment, as in other addictions. Some narcissistic patients may appear to be highly functional and successful, vain and self-confident, but they harbor deep, albeit latent, fears of inadequacy and are overly dependent on the admiration of others they devalue for their stability; Other patients may present as socially isolated, self-effacing, and symptomatic, reacting with anger and shame when their unrealistic beliefs are challenged, with private feelings arising from the sanctification of suffering or a latent sense of superiority (Diamond et al., 2021).

It has been stated that unconscious disorders play an important role in the formation of this pathology and affecting interpersonal relationships in individuals exhibiting narcissistic personality traits (Dimaggio et al., 2002). In addition, it has been stated that individuals with Narcissistic Personality Disorder have difficulty recognizing the emotions and thoughts that constitute their mental state and have difficulty establishing a connection between internal functions and the external world (Dimaggio et al., 2007). In studies that divide students according to age groups, it has been stated that younger students have higher narcissistic tendencies (Gezer, 2017)). Based on the results of this study, one of the limitations of our study is that the volunteers were not divided into age groups.

Conclusion

According to the results obtained in our study, it was observed that as the number of years of sports activity increased, the rate of narcissistic personality traits in individuals

increased. The lack of a difference in awareness about exercise addiction in students who do not exercise regularly and have been doing sports for a long time may cause these students to be vulnerable to potential dangers in their future lives. Researcher think that it may be useful to provide training to increase the awareness level of exercise addiction in university students.

However, since the reasons why people turn to exercise may differ from each other, developing methods that can evaluate these differences together may be important in understanding and treating exercise addiction.

Recommendations

Conducting multifactorial evaluations that may lead to the emergence of exercise addiction in university students and planning awareness training for exercise addiction with the results obtained from these evaluations can help establish balance in the social lives of these students.

Kısaltmalar / Abbreviations

F	Frekans
N	Sample size (Örneklem büyüklüğü)
\bar{X}	Mean (Ortalama)
Ss	Standard deviation (SD) (Standart sapma)
F	F-ratio (ANOVA test statistic) (F değeri)
P	P-value (Anlamlılık değeri)

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma ve yazım sürecinde "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş olup; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamış ve bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir. Makale ile ilgili doğabilecek her türlü ihlallerde sorumluluk yazara aittir.

In the preparation and writing process of this study, scientific, ethical, and citation principles outlined in the "Directive on Scientific Research and Publication Ethics of Higher Education Institutions" have been strictly followed. No falsification has been made on the collected data, and this study has not been submitted to any other academic publication medium for evaluation. The author assumes full responsibility for any potential violations related to the article.

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

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